

SYNTHESIS OF SOME 2-THIO-3-(SUBSTITUTED) BENZYL- QUINAZOLINE-2 : 4(1H, 3H)-DIONES

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Thioquinazolones are physiologically active compounds. Gujral and Saxena (*Chem. Abst.*, 1956, 50, 6662) tested some 2-alkyl-3-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolones and found them active as ataractic agents. Buzas and Hoffman (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1959, 1889) also synthesised 2-alkyl-3-substituted-4(3H)-quinazolones as potential hypnotics and analgesics. Very recently McCarty *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 964) prepared a series of 2-alkylthio-3-phenyl (or allyl)-4-(3H)-quinazolones. Benzyl isothiocyanates were first prepared and reported by the present author (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 423), some of which have been patented as bacteriostatic agents (McKay and Garmaise, *Canad. Patent*, No. 579233; *Chem. Abst.*, 1960, 54, 412; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 4328). Since benzyl isothiocyanate moiety will also be present in 2-thio-3-(substituted) benzylquinazoline-2 : 4(1H, 3H)-diones, it is of interest to synthesise a series of these compounds as potential ataractic agents for studying their activity. Table I describes the compounds prepared.

TABLE I

No.	R.	Crystalline nature.	M.P.	% Sulphur	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ *	Colorless needles	246°	11.8	11.9
2°	ℓ-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	..	262°	10.6	10.6
3.	p-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	..	226°	10.5	10.6
4.	p-BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	..	220°	9.1	9.2
5.	p-IC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	..	268-70°	7.9	8.1
6.	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	Colorless granules	216°	11.1	11.3
7.	(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CH ₂ (2:5)	.. needles**	259-60°	10.7	10.8
8.	(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CH ₂ (2:4)	Yellowish granules	235°	10.6	10.8

* Repeated crystallisation from benzene and ethanol.

** Required six hours' refluxing.

General Method of Preparation.—Substituted benzyl isothiocyanates (0.1M), dissolved in absolute ethanol, were slowly added to an ethanolic solution of anthranilic acid (0.1M.) in a r.b. flask, and the reaction mixture refluxed on a water bath until the smell of isothiocyanate disappeared (usually 2-3 hours). The reaction product was transferred to a beaker and the alcohol allowed to evaporate whereupon crystalline thioquinazolones separated out. These were recrystallised from ethanol until analytically pure samples were obtained. The compounds prepared are listed in the table. All melting points are uncorrected.

Synthesis of 2-alkyl and aryl thio-3-substituted benzylthioquinazolones, their hydrolysis to obtain the corresponding quinazoline diones and synthesis of 1:3-thiazines from these compounds are in progress and will be communicated in future.

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